

Physico-Chemical Investigation on the Complexes of Indium(III) with Ligands Containing Oxygen as Donor Atoms

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Potentiometric studies have been carried out on the complexes of indium (III) with acetylacetone, benzoylacetone, malonic acid and phthalic acid. The Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique as used by Irving and Rossotti, has been applied to determine the stepwise formation constants of the complexes. The log K values have been computed by least squares method. The values of changes in ΔG , ΔH and ΔS accompanying complex formation have been evaluated at three different temperatures at an ionic strength 0.2M (NaClO₄). The results obtained indicate that if any anomalous change in the particular complex occurs due to steric or solvation factors then the effect due to these factors is reflected in the enthalpy and entropy changes associated with the metal-ligand coordination reactions.

ACETYLACETONE and benzoylacetone belong to a class of compounds known as β -diketones. A number of studies have been made on the β -diketones complexes formed with bivalent metal ions and rare earth elements.¹⁻⁶ Complex forming tendency of indium(III) with acetylacetone using extraction methods has also been reported.⁷⁻⁹ Polarographic behaviour of indium(III) - acetylacetone has been studied by Cosovic and Branica⁹. Recently, the gas chromatographic behaviour of In(III) chelates with various β -diketones including benzoylacetone and acetylacetone has been reported by Utsunomlya.¹⁰ Regarding dicarboxylic acids, Nair and Nancollas¹¹ were the first to communicate the thermodynamic parameters of ion association of some transition metal malonates. Equilibrium studies of complexes formed with malonic acid and phthalic acid have been reported by different group of workers¹²⁻¹⁷. However no reference is available on the potentiometric studies and thermodynamic characteristics of In(III) chelates formed with acetylacetone and benzoylacetone in 50% aqueous-dioxan media and with malonic acid and phthalic acid in aqueous media.

In the present communication are reported the "practical" proton-ligand stability constants and stepwise metal-ligand stability constants of above systems at various temperatures obtained by Calvin-Bjerrum titration techniques¹⁸⁻¹⁹ as used by Irving and Rossotti²⁰. The stepwise free energy changes (ΔG), enthalpy changes (ΔH) and entropy changes (ΔS) associated with the complex forming reactions have been evaluated at 25°, 35° and 45° in an ionic strength 0.2M (NaClO₄). The chelates formed with acetylacetone (ACA) and benzoylacetone (BNA) have been studied in 50% dioxan media whereas those formed with malonic acid (MLA) and phthalic acid (PTHA) have been studied in aqueous media.

The results obtained have been discussed in detail with reference to the results already reported in literature.

Experimental

Materials: Metal solution: A stock solution (0.02M) of In(NO₃)₃·5H₂O (Schachardt, Munchen) was prepared in a calculated quantity of perchloric acid to prevent hydrolysis of metal ions. The metal content was estimated by precipitation of indium as 8-hydroxyquinolate²¹.

Ligand solutions: The stock solution (0.015M) of ACA (B.D.H.) was prepared both in double distilled water and in purified dioxan as the studies have been carried out in 100% water as well as in 50% dioxan-water media. The purity of ACA was checked by determining the refractive index (reported 1.45178; observed 1.4518). Due to the insolubility of BNA (Fluka) in water, the stock solution (0.015M) was prepared, in purified dioxan by direct weighing. MLA and PTHA both of B.D.H. make were used and their stock solution (0.02M) were prepared in double distilled water. The concentration was estimated by titrating a small portion of these solutions potentiometrically.

Sodium hydroxide-Sodium hydroxide (Merck) was dissolved in carbon dioxide free, doubly distilled water in a Pyrex vessel. The solution was kept overnight. A portion of the solution was diluted and its concentration was determined by titrating a portion of it potentiometrically against standard (0.1M) potassium hydrogen phthalate.

Sodium perchlorate: A solution of sodium perchlorate was prepared by dissolving AnalAR (Riedel) NaClO₄·H₂O in doubly distilled water.

Perchloric acid : AnalaR (Merck) was diluted to prepare a stock solution (0.1M) which was titrated potentiometrically against standard sodium hydroxide solution to determine its concentration.

Dioxan : AnalaR (B.D.H.) dioxan was purified²² before use, by refluxing it over excess of sodium for 6-12 hours and collecting the fraction distilling at 101-102°. The purity was ascertained by determining the refractive index which was found to be 1.439 against the reported value of 1.437 at 25°.

Apparatus : A pH-meter (Beckman model H-2) with a glass-calomel electrode assembly was used to determine the change in hydrogen ion concentration of the solution. The saturated calomel electrode was connected to the cell externally by means of agar bridge saturated with KNO₃ to prevent the formation of chloro complexes. The design of the cell was such that it allowed flushing of nitrogen (presaturated with solvent) through the solution and also enabled measurements to be carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen.

metal complexes by this method, it is essential to have a prior knowledge of the "practical" proton-ligand stability constants. The values of \bar{n}_A at various pH meter readings (B) were calculated from the acid and ligand titration curves. The equation (1) as used by Irving and Rossotti was employed :

$$\bar{n}_A = \left\{ Y T^{\circ}_{CL} + \frac{(V' - V'')(N + E^{\circ})}{(V^{\circ} + V')} \right\} T^{\circ}_{CL} \quad (1)$$

where V'' and V' denote that volume of alkali added to reach the same value of pH (B) in the titration of ligand and acid respectively; T[°]_{CL} is the total ligand concentration, Y the number of replaceable protons attached to the ligand, N the normality of alkali, E[°] the initial concentration of the free acid and \bar{n}_A is the average number of protons attached per ligand ion.

The values of concentrations, V[°] and Y used for these calculations for various ligands have been summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF CONCENTRATIONS ; V[°] AND Y FOR VARIOUS LIGANDS

Ligand	V [°]	Y	N	E [°] × 10 ²	T [°] _{CL} × 10 ² Moles/litre	T [°] _{CM} × 10 ³
ACA	75	1	1.020	1.014	5.219	1.067
ACA*	75	1	1.020	1.014	4.964	1.067
BNA*	75	1	1.020	1.014	5.168	1.067
MLA	100	2	1.020	1.035	4.947	1.045
PTHA	100	2	1.020	1.055	4.693	1.050

*experiments in 50% dioxan

Temperature was maintained by immersing the cell in an electrically maintained thermostat having a regulating accuracy of ± 0.2°.

Bjerrum-Calvin Titration : Three mixtures were prepared as follows : Mixture A : perchloric acid ; Mixture B : perchloric acid + ligand solution ; Mixture C : perchloric acid + ligand solution + metal solution, such that the concentrations of the common ingredients were identical in different cases. An appropriate amount of neutral sodium perchlorate was added to maintain the desired ionic strength. The volumes of the three mixtures were adjusted identical, using double distilled water or dioxan. The small contraction, during mixing, in the total volume of the solution was considered to be negligible for water-dioxan mixtures. The ratio between the metal salt and the ligands was such that, the maximum coordination number of the metal ion can be satisfied. A graph between pH-meter reading 'B' and the volume of alkali added was plotted. The three titration curves obtained were referred to as (A) acid titration curve, (B) ligand titration curve and (C) complex titration curve.

Results

"Practical" Proton-Ligand Stability Constants. : In order to calculate the formation constants of the

The calculation of the "practical" stability constants of the proton complexes was carried out by plotting a graph of \bar{n}_A against pH (B) and then applying various computational methods²².

The curves obtained from function \bar{n}_A (B) were extended between 0 and 1 in the \bar{n}_A scale for ACA and BNA indicating the dissociation of HACA and HBNA as follows :

The formation curves for MLA and PTHA were found to be extended between 0 and 2 in the \bar{n}_A scale indicating the dissociation of H₂MLA and H₂PTHA as follows :

The values of log K^H (± 0.03) in case of ACA and BNA have been calculated by using two methods, (A) interpolation at half \bar{n}_A value and (B) interpolation at various \bar{n}_A values. In the calculation of log K^H and

TABLE 2—"PRACTICAL" PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS IN $\mu = 0.2M$ (NaClO_4)

Ligand	Constants	t=25°		t=35°		t=45°	
		Method		Method		Method	
		(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)
ACA	log K^H	8.97	8.98	8.88	8.88	8.78	8.78
ACA*	log K^H	9.55	9.55	9.48	9.48	9.41	9.41
BNA*	log K^H	9.80	9.80	9.70	9.71	9.63	9.62
MLA	log K^H	—	5.17	—	5.24	—	5.30
	log K^H_4	—	2.70	—	2.69	—	2.67
	log β^H	—	7.87	—	7.93	—	7.97
PTHA	log K^H	—	4.82	—	4.86	—	4.89
	log K^H_2	—	2.71	—	2.74	—	2.77
	log β^H	—	7.53	—	7.60	—	7.66

*experiments in 50% dioxan

log K^H_2 for MLA and PTHA, the method of interpolation at various \bar{n}_A values was employed. The values obtained at various temperatures and at $\mu = 0.2$ for all these ligands are summarised in Table 2.

Metal-Ligand Stability Constants: For a metal complex or chelate formation, taking place in steps in a homogenous solution, the step formation constants are given by equation (6)

$$K_n = C_{ML_n} / C_{ML_{n-1}} \cdot C_L \quad (n = 1, 2, \dots, N) \quad \dots (6)$$

where K_n is called the n th metal-ligand stability constant.

In the present case the formation constants have been obtained by the analysis of the formation curves obtained by plotting \bar{n} against pL . The value of \bar{n} the average number of ligands attached per metal ion is calculated from the equation(7)

$$\bar{n} = (V''' - V'')(N + E^0) / (V^0 + V') \bar{n}_A T^0_{CM} \quad (7)$$

where T^0_{CM} denotes the total concentration of metal present in solution and other terms have their usual meanings.

The free ligand exponent p^L has been calculated from equation (8)

$$p^L = \text{Log} \left[\frac{\sum_{n=0}^{n=j} P \beta_n^H (1/\text{antilog } B)(V^0 + V''')}{(T^0_{CL} - \bar{n} T^0_{CM})V_0} \right] \quad (8)$$

where $P \beta_n^H$ is the overall "practical" proton-ligand stability constant.

It was observed in the complex forming systems of In(III) with ACA, BNA, MLA and PTHA that the metal titration curves did not join up parallel to the ligand titration curves indicating liberation of extra

protons due to the hydrolysis of metal ions. Precipitation was observed for ACA in water media at pH 5.0, ACA in 50% dioxan media at pH 5.0, BNA at pH 5.0, MLA at pH 4.5 and PTHA at pH 3.8. Hence, in order to preclude errors due to hydrolysis in the calculation of \bar{n} , only the lower pH regions of titration curves were used. The \bar{n} values used to calculate the stability constants of the complexes were not considered above $pH \sim 4.0$ in case of ACA and MLA complexes in water media, $pH \sim 4.2$ in case of ACA and BNA complexes in 50% dioxan media and 3.8 in case of PTHA complexes. The formation curves drawn

Fig. 1. Formation Curves of In(III)-ACA (aqueous) complex at ionic strength 0.2

Fig. 2. Formation Curves of In(III)-ACA (dioxan) complex at ionic strength 0.2

Fig. 4. Formation Curves of In(III)-MLA complex at ionic strength 0.2

Fig. 3. Formation Curves of In(III)-BNA complex at ionic strength 0.2

Fig. 5. Formation Curves of In(III)-PTHA complex at ionic strength 0.2

between \bar{n} and pL for the complexes formed by In(III) with ACA in water (Fig. 1); ACA in dioxan (50%) (Fig. 2); BNA (Fig. 3); MLA (Fig. 4) are found to be extended between 0 and 2 in the \bar{n} scale. In all these cases from the shapes of the formation curves it is apparent that the stepwise formation of complexes is not independent. Hence, the stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ have been calculated by the least squares method. The formation curves drawn between \bar{n} and pL for the complexes formed by In(III) with PTHA are extending between 0 and 1 in the \bar{n} scale (Fig. 5). Thus, the value of $\log K$ has been evaluated by the method of interpolation at half \bar{n} value.

The values of $\log K_1$ (± 0.03) and $\log K_2$ (± 0.05) for the complexes formed by In(III) with ACA, BNA, MLA and PTHA at various temperatures and $\mu=0.2$ are summarised in Table 3.

Thermodynamic Parameters: The values of the changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been calculated at three different temperatures and ionic strength $0.2M$ ($NaClO_4$) with the help of temperature coefficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz

equation²⁴. The equation (9) relating the stability constant to the free energy change of the reaction was employed for evaluating the value of the free energy change at various temperatures

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K \quad \dots (9)$$

The value of the enthalpy change (ΔH) has been determined from the slope of the curve obtained by plotting $\log K$ against $1/T$. This resulted in a straight line indicating that the assumption in the Gibbs-Helmholtz equation, that ΔH is constant at different temperatures is true. The value of the enthalpy change (ΔH) was evaluated by equating the slope to $-\Delta H/4.75$.

The entropy change (ΔS) of the reaction was calculated at three different temperatures from the equation (10)

$$\Delta S = (\Delta H - \Delta G)/T \quad \dots (10)$$

The values of stepwise free energy changes (ΔG), enthalpy changes (ΔH), and entropy changes (ΔS) calculated at three different temperatures viz. 25° , 35° , and 45° and $\mu=0.2$ have been summarised in Table 4.

TABLE 3—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS IN $\mu=0.2$ ($NaClO_4$)

Complex	Constants	$t=25^\circ$	$t=35^\circ$	$t=45^\circ$
In(III)—ACA	$\log K_1$	7.71	7.61	7.51
	$\log K_2$	6.81	6.69	6.57
	$\log \beta$	14.52	14.30	14.08
In(III)—ACA*	$\log K_1$	8.30	8.22	8.14
	$\log K_2$	7.55	7.46	7.38
	$\log \beta$	15.85	15.68	15.52
In(III)—BNA*	$\log K_1$	8.81	8.71	8.62
	$\log K_2$	8.02	7.90	7.78
	$\log \beta$	16.83	16.61	16.40
In(III)—MLA	$\log K_1$	5.80	5.92	6.06
	$\log K_2$	3.51	3.58	3.66
	$\log \beta$	9.31	9.50	9.72
In(III)—PTHA	$\log K_1$	3.87	3.96	4.03

*experiments in 50% dioxan media

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF In(III) COMPLEXES AT $\mu=0.2$

Complex	Reaction Step	Temp. °C	ΔG_n ΔH_n		ΔS_n e.u.
			Kcal/mole		
In(III)—ACA	n=1	25	-10.52	-4.0	+22
		35	-10.73		
		45	-10.92		
	n=2	25	-9.28	-4.9	+15
		35	-9.43		
		45	-9.56		
In(III)—ACA*	n=1	25	-11.14	-3.2	+28
		35	-11.59		
		45	-11.84		
	n=2	25	-10.29	-3.7	+22
		35	-10.52		
		45	-10.74		
In(III)—BNA*	n=1	25	-12.01	-4.1	+27
		35	-12.27		
		45	-12.54		
	n=2	25	-10.93	-4.9	+20
		35	-11.13		
		45	-11.32		
In(III)—MLA	n=1	25	-7.91	+4.9	+43
		35	-8.34		
		45	-8.82		
	n=2	25	-4.79	+3.3	+27
		35	-5.05		
		45	-5.32		
In(III)—PTHA	n=1	25	-5.28	+3.2	+28
		35	-5.58		
		45	-5.86		
		45	-5.86		

*experiments in 50% dioxan

The precision of ΔG values is ± 0.05 K cal/mole for the first step and ± 0.08 Kcal/mole for the second step. The error limits of ΔH values are ± 0.5 Kcal/mole for the first step and ± 1.0 Kcal/mole for the subsequent steps. The ΔS values are having deviations of ± 2 cal/deg/mole for the first complex forming reaction and for the subsequent complexes the deviations are of the order of ± 3 cal/deg/mole.

Discussion

The nature of the formation curve for ACA in water and in dioxan+water medium is similar (Fig 1 and 2). Thus, it is reasonable to assume that the solvation sphere of metal ion and the metal complexes in 50% dioxan (which still contains more moles of water than of dioxan) is the same as that in water due to more polar nature of the water dipoles as compared to the dioxan dipoles and the low concentration of the solutes.

It is observed that the formation of indium(III) complexes of acetylacetone in 50% dioxan is accompanied by larger changes in entropy as compared to that in 100% water. The increased stability or free energy change for the formation of these complexes in dioxan+water medium arises as a result of difference in the standard states chosen for the two solutions and is due to a larger value of the entropy change, which more than compensates the decrease in the magnitude of $-\Delta H$.

From the various relationships given between thermodynamic parameters and dielectric constant, the following general correlations can be obtained for the reactions,

1. ΔG has a negative sign and its magnitude will decrease as the dielectric constant of the medium decreases. Hence as shown in Table 4 the decrease in ΔG accompanying the formation of $\text{In}(\text{ACA})_2^{2+}$ in 50% dioxan medium is higher than that in 100% water medium.

2. ΔS has a positive sign and its magnitude will increase with a decrease in the dielectric constant. If the "iceberg" concept of Evans and Frank²⁰ is applied to the dioxan+water medium, interaction between solvent dipoles and a metal ion will be of two types, (a) between those "frozen" water dipoles which are replaced by ligand molecules during complex formation, (b) between more distant water and dioxan dipoles which are oriented as a result of the electric field of the metal ions. For a metal complex dissolved in media of different dielectric constants, e.g. 100% water or 50% dioxan the interaction (a) will not change very much, a state of saturation will exist as far as the entropy changes are concerned. The "frozen" dipoles

contributing the solvation sphere of an ion consist entirely of the more polar water molecules; but the effect due to (b) will cause much greater entropy change, on neutralisation of the charges on the cations and anions during complex formation in dioxan + water medium as compared to 100% water.

3. A lowering in the dielectric constant will increase the magnitude of the endothermic contribution. It may be seen from Table 4 that the exothermic heat of formation is lower in 50% dioxan than in water for the In(III)-ACA complexes.

The enthalpy changes accompanying the formation of BNA complexes of In(III) in 50% dioxan are more than ACA complexes. This is also the order of stability or the free energy change. The stepwise enthalpies of chelate formation ΔH_1 and ΔH_2 are equal (Table 4) within the limits of experimental error. This is in general agreement with the results reported in literature²⁶ and in agreement with the thermochemical cycle of Yatsimirskii and Grinberg²⁷. Main contributing effect which remains constant is the difference between the heats of vaporisation of ligand and of displaced water. The only change is in the charge of the ion which will bring about a change in ΔS .

It has also been shown by N.M.R. studies²⁸ that in benzoylacetone, the phenyl ring is coplanar with the hydrogen bonded enolic ring and hence it is able to increase the electron density on the adjacent oxygen atoms by resonance. These more basic donor oxygen atoms will therefore, form more covalent O-M bonds by virtue of their higher electron density and will lead to the greater negative values of ΔH for BNA complexes than ACA. This is consistent with the observed results of ΔH .

It is also noted that the entropy changes for the formation of bisketonato In(III) complexes with ACA and BNA are constant to ± 2 e.u. in the dioxan + water medium. This indicates that the stereochemical arrangement of the ligands around the In(III) ion for these complexes in dioxan + water medium is similar. The present results therefore, confirm the conclusions of Nakamoto et. al.²⁹ who showed by I.R. studies that phenyl substitution increases the strength of O-M bond in the β -diketone complexes.

It is seen from the present results that the malonate complexes formed with In(III) are having greater stability than phthalate complexes. This may be due to the fact that latter involves less stable seven-membered chelate ring as compared to six-membered ring in case of former. The enthalpies of formation of metal dicarboxylate complexes involving malonate and phthalate ions are endothermic. In spite of these unfavourable enthalpy changes the complexes are stabilised by relatively large positive entropy change due to the liberation of water molecules from the ions accompanying complex formation.

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References

1. R. M. IZATT, C. G. HAAS (JR.), B. P. BLOCK and W. C. FERNELIUS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 1133.
2. V. V. SUKHAN, E. UHJEMANN and L. WOLF, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1967, 12(2), 455.
3. R. M. IZATT, W. C. FERNELIUS and B. P. BLOCK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 80, 235.
4. L. G. VAN UITERT, W. C. FERNELIUS and B. E. DOUGLAS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 457, 2736.
5. I. PRASILOVA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, 26(4), 661.
6. H. YONEDA, G. R. CHOPPIN, J. L. BEAR and J. V. QUAGLIANO, *Inorg. Ohem.*, 1964, 3(11), 1642.
7. N. P. RUDENKO and I. STRAY, *Trudy komissi Anal. Khim. Akad. Nauk SSSR, Inst. Geokhim. Anal. Khim.*, 1958, 9, 28.
8. J. F. STEINBACH and H. FREISER, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1954, 26(2), 375.
9. B. COSOVIC and M. BRANICA, *J. Polarographic Soc.*, 1966, 12(1), 5; 1966, 12(3), 97.
10. KEI UTSUNOMIYA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1971, 44(10), 2688.
11. V. S. K. NAIR and G. H. NANCOLLAS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4367.
12. K. S. RAJAN and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, 29(2), 523.
13. S. RAMAMURTHY and M. SANTAPPA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1969, 42(2), 411.
14. V. T. ATHAVALE, N. MAHADEVAN, P. K. MATHUR and R. M. SATHE, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, 29(8), 1947.
15. A. K. BHATTACHARYA and G. S. RAO, *J. Physik. Chem.*, 1962, 219, 11.
16. N. K. DUTT and P. BOSE, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1958, 295, 131.
17. I. R. DESAI and V. S. K. NAIR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 2360.
18. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", (Haase : Copenhagen 1941).

19. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
20. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
21. L. ERDEY, "Gravimetric Analysis," *Inst. Ser. of Monographs analyt. Chem. Vol. 7* (Pergamon: New York 1965).
22. A. I. VOGEL, "Practical Organic Chemistry" (Longmans Publication: London 1971).
23. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
24. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and V. P. VASIL'EV, "Instability constants of Complex Compounds" (Pergamon: New York 1960).
25. M. S. EVANS and H. S. FRANK, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, 13, 507.
26. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKIN, "Modern Coordination Chemistry" (Interscience: New York 1960).
27. A. A. GRINBERG and K. B. YATSIMIRSKII, *Bull. Acad. Sci. U.S.S.R. Div. Chem. Sci.*, 1952, 239.
28. R. L. LINTVEDT and H. F. HOLTZCLAW, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 239.
29. K. NAKAMOTO, Y. MORIMOTO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 346.
30. H. F. HOLTZCLAW and J. P. COLLMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 75, 3318.
31. H. F. HOLTZCLAW, A. H. GARLSON and J. P. COLLMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 1838.